

Creeping Leader Surface Spark Discharge on Low-Conductive Natural and Artificial Objects

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Abstract—How can the lightning strike into a dry tree be explained or is the starting of an upward leader discharge at a towering object of insulating material possible? These electrical discharge processes can be explained by creeping spark and flashover at the air-insulator interface on these objects. For this, a network modelling approach for the creeping discharge is presented and based on the theoretical investigations as well as scaled experiments, it could be shown that a rapidly propagating creeping discharge leads to a flashover of the object made of insulating material in times significantly shorter than a microsecond and subsequently an upward leader can start immediately from its tip.

Index Terms—lightning strike on parched trees or on stone houses; creeping leader spark; surface discharge

I. INTRODUCTION TO LIGHTNING ON INSULATOR ROD

Tall and low-conductive objects like parched trees, stony mountain tops, pure stone houses, or structures without metallic parts (only made of bricks or wood) should not be susceptible to lightning strikes. However, such lightning strikes are known from [1], [2], [3], [4]. So the question arises, as to how these lightning strikes can be explained, when these towering objects are to be considered as quasi non-conducting, which can be simplified to a rod or a thin cylinder of insulating material, see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Insulator rod with lightning strike vertically on ideal conductive plane

The process of a lightning strike of an insulating material rod standing on a well-conducting grounded plate can be described as follows. When the tip of the downward leader has reached a short distance (a few 100 m) from the ground, a sufficiently high background electric field strength occurs (Fig. 2), so that a discharge ignites at the surface of the

insulator rod and from this a creeping discharge starts on the insulator-air interface.

According to Fig. 2, an increased field strength occurs at the tip (upper end) of the insulating material rod in the almost homogeneous background field, which can cause the discharge.

Fig. 2: Insulating material rod on ideally conducting ground in homogeneous background field (rotationally symmetrical, r - z plane) – color: magnitude of electric field strength, lines: equipotential surfaces

More likely, however, the ignition of a discharge may also be caused by field enhancement in the triple junction/gusset (Fig. 3) on the ground surface, in an air gap, presuming field displacement occurs due to $\epsilon_{r,air} < \epsilon_{r,ins}$.

Fig. 3: Insulator rod with air gap at lower end (right: magnification) on ideally conducting ground in homogeneous background field – electric field strength (rotationally symmetric, r - z plane)

This creeping discharge grows upwards at high speed on the rod surface and reaches the upper tip after a short period of time. Charges and the potential of the ground are thus

carried to the tip of the insulator rod. The creeping spark ending on the tip of the insulator rod means that there is already an occurring or existing ionization of the air. Since there is now already a conductive plasma channel and many free moving charge carriers are present at the tip, this spark channel continues to grow beyond the rod as an upward leader towards the downward leader tip. For this, it is necessary that a minimum amount of charge (~ 1 C [5], [6], [7]) or a significant current (~ 1 A...100 A) has already flown into the creeping spark. One can also imagine that the start of a creeping leader spark at the ground corresponds to the start of the upward (connecting) leader on this arrangement (connecting upward leader development).

After joining of the upward and downward leader, the first return stroke and possibly subsequent return strokes occur, using the highly conductive channel of the original creeping spark for charge dissipation to ground.

II. MODELLING OF CREEPING SPARK DISCHARGE AND FLASHOVER AT SOLID INSULATING MATERIAL INTERFACE

The onset of discharges takes place in the thin, narrow gas space or air gap from the gusset of the almost transversely layered dielectric (field displacement into the gaseous insulating material with lower permittivity) and the creeping discharge subsequently spreads upwards in the direction of the electric field at the longitudinal boundary layer of solid and gaseous insulating material. The driving force is the tangential electric field component acting on the vertical insulator cylinder assembly (tangential = parallel to the interface).

A. Field Enhancement in Triple Junction

In the vicinity of the triple junction (gusset), a discharge can start in air and thus the creeping discharge on the surface of the insulating material rod and the discharge will spread in the direction to the tip of the rod. A gusset can already be present due to a chamfer, a beveled lower edge of the rod, or a rounding of the lower circumferential edge of the rod.

If $\epsilon_{r,air}$ in the sharp angle is smaller than $\epsilon_{r,ins}$ in the adjacent solid insulating material, then theoretically the field strength in the triple junction is infinitely large. However, if the surface of the solid insulating material is conductive (pollution), the field strength is reduced. [8], [9]

The initiation of partial discharges occurs in the gusset when the field strength for the discharge onset of $E > E_{d,air} \approx 30$ kV/cm is exceeded [10] [11].

According to [11], the partial discharge onset voltage u_{pd} can be estimated with the insulation thickness d_{ins} .

$$u_{pd} \sim \sqrt{\frac{d_{ins}}{\epsilon_{r,ins}}} \quad u_{pd} [\text{kV}] = K \cdot \left(d_{ins} [\text{cm}] \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{r,air}}{\epsilon_{r,ins}} \right)^a \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{r,air} = 1.0 \quad a = 0.45 \dots 0.5 \quad K = 8 \quad \text{for air}$$

$$d_{ins} = 2 \text{ cm} \quad \text{e.g. } \epsilon_{r,ins} = 3.8 \quad \text{for Polyoxymethylene}$$

With $a = 0.5$ results a comparatively small partial discharge onset voltage of $u_{pd} = 5.8$ kV, which is certainly reached

without verification already at a low background field strength E_0 . An estimation of the electric field strength according to [8], [9] comes to the same result: An insulating sphere with spherical radius R lies with point contact on a plate electrode and generates a triple junction in air. The following values are assumed $\epsilon_{r,ins} = 3.8$, $\epsilon_{r,air} = 1.0$, $U = 1$ kV, $R = d_{ins}/2 = 1$ cm. This gives the background field strength $E_0 = U/R = 1$ kV/cm and the field strength at the contact point in the solid material

$$E_{ins} = \frac{E_0}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{\epsilon_{r,ins}}{\epsilon_{r,air}} + 1 \right) = 2.4 \frac{\text{kV}}{\text{cm}} \quad (2)$$

and the field strength at the contact point in air

$$E_{air} = \frac{E_0}{2} \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{r,ins}}{\epsilon_{r,air}} \cdot \left(\frac{\epsilon_{r,ins}}{\epsilon_{r,air}} + 1 \right) = 9.1 \frac{\text{kV}}{\text{cm}} \quad (3)$$

Thus, at the same time, the field strength increase in the gusset $E_{air} \gg E_0$ ($E_{ins} > E_0$) becomes clear.

B. Capacitive Equivalent Circuit Diagram for Insulator Rod

For a vertical insulator rod in homogeneous background field, a capacitive equivalent circuit can be set up, which can also be modified for an existing creeping discharge. A first consideration is shown in Fig. 4, where the remote counter-electrode (top plate) is depicted and the homogeneous downward directed background field strength E_0 is shown below. The lower plate electrode has the potential $\varphi = 0$, thus representing the electrical surface conductor or the ideal ground.

Fig. 4: Model illustration of the propagation of creeping discharges on an insulator rod starting from the metal plate/ground up to the tip of the rod

Two different basic variants in Fig. 4 for the propagation of creeping discharges on the surface of the insulator rod from the metal plate or from ground to the rod tip are conceivable:

- (a) Essentially a thin channel (creeping leader stem with streamer tuft) on the insulating material rod.
- (b) Creeping discharge as a cylindrical shell ("tube") around the insulating material rod.

C. Electric Field Distortion Due To the Upward Leader Channel Along an Insulator Rod

To validate the concept of modelling the discharge process as distributed capacitances along electric field lines (variant (a) of Sec. II-B), FEM simulations of the time and spatial varying electric field were carried out considering the upward growth of the leader channel. This takes into account the dynamic field shifts as a result of resistive-capacitive balancing processes. The geometry of the simulated model in Fig. 5 is based on the scaled down experiments in Sec. III.

Fig. 5: FEM-Model of the experiments in Sec. III for the calculation of the time and spatial varying electric field distribution under consideration of an upward leader channel

As in the experiments, at the upper sphere a switching impulse voltage is applied. The voltage source is modelled by the equivalent circuit of the pulse generator used in the experiments, so the energy is limited by the charged capacitance (10 nF). On the grounded lower electrode, an insulator rod is modelled with $\epsilon_r = 3.8$ and $\sigma_{ins} = 1 \times 10^{-14} \text{ S/m}$ (material is POM). The surrounding air is assumed to be $\epsilon_r = 1.0$ and $\sigma_{air} < \sigma_{ins}$. The upward leader channel is modelled as dedicated geometry object ($\alpha = \pm 5^\circ$ of the $x-y$ -plane, thickness 0.5 mm) with time and space varying electrical conductivity. Starting at $t_{BD} = 138.75 \mu\text{s}$ (beginning of the breakdown in the experiment, see Fig. 12) the electrical conductivity of the channel is set to $\sigma_{dis} \gg \sigma_{ins}$ for a discharge height growing over time ($z(t)$). Above the discharge height, the conductivity is that of air. This allows to model any upward leader velocity function without in-depth consideration of the physical breakdown process. Based on the specific breakdown duration of the experiments, the upward leader velocity is assumed to be constant at $0.667 \text{ m}/\mu\text{s}$. Fig. 6 shows the discharge channel expanding upwards over time as plot of the electrical conductivity in space. Fig. 7 gives the electric field lines at 100 ns after t_{BD} in the $x-z$ - and $y-z$ -planes. The upward leader channel is in the $y-z$ -plane and the discharge height for this time is 64 mm. In other words, at $t = 138.846 \mu\text{s}$ the discharge channel ends 4 mm above the apex of the insulator rod.

Fig. 6: Evolution of the discharge channel over time plotted as electrical conductivity (x-scale zoomed 3 times)

Fig. 7: Electric field distortion due to the highly conductive upward growing discharge channel at $t = 138.846 \mu\text{s}$ (color: magnitude of electric potential, lines: electric field lines)

In Fig. 7b the distortion of the electric field due to the highly conductive upward moving leader channel in this plane is clearly visible. The leader channel carries the ground potential upwards so that the field lines terminate at the discharge channel. In comparison the electric field in the perpendicular plane (Fig. 7a) is not distorted due to the leader channel and remains symmetric.

D. Network Model With Capacitances for Creeping Leader Discharge on Insulator Rod

Based on the results of the electric field distortion simulations (Sec. II-C), the development of a creeping leader spark on the surface of an insulator rod due to a homogenous electric background field can be represented by a circuit model of distributed capacitances as shown in Fig. 8. The capacitances were oriented according to the field lines (Fig. 7).

The parameters and the pre-calculation of values for the equivalent capacitance circuit model in Fig. 8 are as follows, whereby the formulas for the capacitances were taken from [12], [13], [14] and adapted.

- $\epsilon_{r,air} = 1.0$ – relative permittivity of air;
- $\epsilon_{r,ins} = 3.8$ – relative permittivity of the insulator (material of the insulator rod is POM);
- $R_L = 25$ mm – radius of sphere electrode ("downward leader tip");
- $H_L = 100$ mm – distance of electrodes ("height of downward leader tip above ground surface");
- $R_R = 5$ mm – radius of the insulator rod;
- $H_R = 60$ mm – height of the insulator rod;
- $\alpha = 2\pi/360 \cong 10^\circ$ – angular width of the creeping spark on the cylinder surface;
- $w_\alpha = \alpha \cdot R_R \approx 0.175$ mm – perimeter segment width (arc length) of the creeping spark on the cylinder surface;
- $m = 20$ – number of vertical differential height elements of the insulator rod;
- $\Delta z = H_R/m = 3$ mm – thickness of the differential height element of the insulator rod;
- $E_{air,0} = U_{peak}/H_L = 10.7$ kV/cm – field strength of the homogenous (background) field;
- $C_{air,0} = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,air} \cdot \frac{\pi \cdot R_L^2}{H_L} \approx 0.695$ pF – capacitance of the homogenous (background) field;
- $C_{air,1} = \frac{2\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,air}}{\frac{1}{R_R} - \frac{1}{2 \cdot (H_L - H_R)}} \approx 2\pi \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,air} \cdot R_R \approx 0.297$ pF – capacitance of the insulator rod top to the downward leader tip;
- $z = n \cdot \Delta z$, $n = 1 \dots m$, $z = (0)\Delta z \dots H_R$ – increasing height;
- $C_{air,2}(z, n) = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,air} \cdot \frac{2\pi \cdot (R_L + R_R) \cdot 3\Delta z}{H_L} \cdot \frac{z}{H_L} \approx 2$ fF... 45 fF – variable outer capacitance of the insulator rod to the downward leader tip, equation fit to electrostatic FEM-calculations, approximated as parallel plate capacitor with special average area $\pi(R_L + R_R) \cdot 3\Delta z$, with distance of the leader height (H_L), scaled by the ratio of increasing height (z) and leader height, valid for $H_L - H_R \gg \Delta z, R_R$;
- $R_{R,ins}(z, n) = R_R \cdot \sqrt{1 - (z/H_R)^2} = R_R \cdot \sqrt{1 - (n/m)^2}$ – assumed inner radius inside insulator rod for calculation of inner capacitances;
- $C_{ins,v}(z, n) = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,ins} \cdot \frac{\pi R_{R,ins}^2(z, n)}{\Delta z}$ – variable inner vertical capacitance for the insulator rod;
- $C_{ins,h}(z, n) = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,ins} \cdot \frac{2\pi \cdot \Delta z}{\ln(R_R/R_{R,ins}(z, n))}$ – variable inner horizontal capacitance for the insulator rod;
- $C_{ins,h\alpha}(z, n) = \epsilon_0 \cdot \epsilon_{r,ins} \cdot \frac{\alpha \cdot \Delta z}{\ln(R_R/R_{R,ins}(z, n))}$ – variable inner horizontal angular capacitance of the creeping spark on the insulator rod;

Toepler's spark resistance law [15] is used for the creeping leader spark on the surface of the insulator rod.

$$R_F(t) = \frac{k_T \cdot l_F}{Q_F(t)} = \frac{k_T \cdot l_F}{\int_0^t i_F(t^*) dt^*} \quad (4)$$

$Q_F(t)$ – time dependent charge flow into the spark; $i_F(t)$

– time dependent current in the spark; l_F – spark length; $l_F = \Delta z = 3$ mm; k_T – Toepler's empirical spark constant ($k_T = 0.005 \dots 0.006$ V s/m for air, here: $k_T = 0.0055$ V s/m)

Fig. 9 illustrates the modelled equivalent capacitive circuit of the insulator rod and the spark discharge in ATP-EMTP. The discharge is made of a voltage dependent switch ($|v_1 - v_2| > V_{fl,n}$ - flashover voltage) and the spark resistance R_F controlled by the MODELs block, implementing Eq. (4) and the voltage switch control. The flashover voltage per stage is defined by the breakdown field strength of air ($E_{d,air}$) and Δz , resulting in a voltage $V_{fl,n} \approx 9$ kV. Further, the air gap (final jump) is modelled the same way with increased flashover voltage ($V_{fl,fin} = E_{d,air}/(H_L - H_R) \approx 100$ kV... 120 kV).

As applied voltage source, the equivalent circuit of the impulse voltage source used in the experiments (Sec. III) is utilized, with $T_1/T_2 = 250/2500$ μ s – switching impulse voltage, $U_{peak} = 107$ kV – peak voltage ($U_{charge} = 130$ kV).

Fig. 9: Equivalent capacitive circuit of the insulator rod (center) and spark discharge (right) (stages 4 to 19 are omitted)

The calculated discharge process is shown in Fig. 10. The different stages of the modelled discharge ignite, seen as time-shifted voltage breakdowns, consecutively analogous to the height increase z of the creeping spark. The duration of the upward growth of the creeping spark takes about 400 ns.

Fig. 10: Time development of the creeping discharge to flashover in about 400 ns

When the air gap is bridged, the insulator rod and air capacitances discharge into the spark column resulting in a decrease of the spark resistance and steep current rise of the total current at the bottom of the insulator rod and spark column.

III. EXPERIMENTS IN SCALED-DOWN SETUP WITH COMPARATIVELY LOW LIGHTNING IMPULSE VOLTAGE

To validate the network model approach, exemplary measurements have been carried out. The scaled arrangement in the discharge experiments is shown in Fig. 11. A comparatively low switching impulse voltage 250/2500 μs with peak voltage $U_{peak} = 107\text{ kV}$ (charge voltage 130 kV, see Fig. 9) is applied on the sphere-plate electrode system, where the insulator rod was placed directly on the lower grounded plate electrode. The closest sphere-to-plate distance was $s = 100\text{ mm}$. The rod is made of POM with $\epsilon_{r,ins} = 3.8$. Without an insulator rod, no breakdown of the pure air gap occurs at $U_{peak} = 107\text{ kV}$.

Fig. 11: Experimental set-up to show creeping discharges on insulating material rod in weakly inhomogeneous field at impulse voltage

The time characteristic of voltage and current is shown in Fig. 12 for one selected measured discharge process at a switching impulse voltage, where the creeping discharge on the insulator rod and the immediately following breakdown of the air gap occurs shortly before the peak in the voltage front.

Fig. 12: Voltage and current for the creeping discharge on the insulator rod and air breakdown of sphere-plate arrangement at switching impulse voltage

The subprocesses can be derived from temporal enlargement. In the lower diagram of Fig. 12, the pre-growth of the

creeping discharge occurs between **0** and **1** (830 ns \sim 1 A), between **1** and **2** (240 ns \sim 10 A) the breakdown of the remaining air gap and between **2** and **3** (220 ns \sim 620 A) the collapse of the voltage with a "high-current" discharge pulse.

To further investigate the pre-breakdown / current behavior, additional measurements were carried out, utilizing an ultra speed image intensifying camera (PCO HFSC-PRO), see Fig. 13. For the recordings, an exposure time of 10 ns was defined and the delay between two consecutive frames is also 10 ns.

Fig. 13: Images (top), voltage and current (bottom) for the creeping discharge on the insulator rod and air breakdown of sphere-plate arrangement at lightning impulse voltage

From the images in Fig. 13, it is clearly visible, that the discharge process initiates at the grounded plate electrode (a small metal strip was used for alignment to the camera here) and then grows to the tip of the insulator rod (frame 1 and 2). In the current time course, a significant current increase up to about 100 A is noticeable for the time of frame 2, whereas the voltage does not decrease significantly, as no breakdown has occurred until then.

Following in frame 3 and 4, the breakdown of the air gap occurs, while the applied voltage rapidly decreases. At the instant of time for frame 4 the air gap is nearly bridged and afterwards the current steeply increases due to the conductive breakdown channel.

From the ns-imaging, it can be concluded, that initially an upwards growing surface discharge occurs on an insulated object exposed to the almost homogeneous electrical background field of the lightning leader tip, as it was previously supposed. This discharge is associated with a significant current flowing from the grounded surface (earth) into the creeping discharge channel. In this time, the voltage excitation and thus the background field does not change significantly. When the creeping discharge has reached the tip of the insulator rod,

the remaining air gap is bridged and the voltage collapses (breakdown / final jump in lightning strike process).

IV. MODELLING OF CREEPING SPARK DISCHARGE FOR AN ENLARGED OBJECT

Based on the modelling approach above, subsequently a creeping spark discharge and flashover should be modelled for a tall object (real world dimensions), see Fig. 14, including the stepped down leader propagation before.

Fig. 14: Schematic of an insulator rod in an electric field and equivalent capacitance circuit model

The parameters and the pre-calculation of values for the equivalent capacitance circuit model in Fig. 14 are as in Sec. II-D except for: $\epsilon_{r,ins} = 2.4$, $R_L = 5$ m, $H_L = 50$ m, $R_R = 0.01$ m, $H_R = 2$ m, $w_\alpha = \alpha \cdot R_R \approx 1.75$ mm, $\Delta z = 0.1$ m, $E_{air,0} = 0.4$ kV/cm, $C_{air,0} \approx 13.908$ pF, $C_{air,1} \approx 0.5564$ pF, $C_{air,2}(z, n) \approx 1$ fF...20 fF.

Typical characteristic values for a leader channel of several meters length in atmospheric air are according to [16]: minimum leader current $i_L \approx 0.6 \dots 1$ A, voltage gradient of the leader channel $E_L \approx 1.0 \dots 1.5$ kV/cm (initial value 5 kV/cm), leader channel with diameter $d_L < 3$ mm, gas temperature (thermoionization) $T_{gas} \approx 5000$ °C.

Propagation values for a downward stepped leader: mean leader step length $l_{dLs} = 50$ m and mean leader velocity $v_{dLs} = 1/1500 \cdot c = 0.2$ m/ μ s, mean downward stepped leader step duration $t_{dLsd} = l_{dLs}/v_{dLs} = 250$ μ s, $f_{dLsd} = 1/t_{dLsd} = 4$ kHz; average rest time between successive steps $t_{dLsr} = 35$ μ s, $f_{dLsr} = 1/t_{dLsr} = 28.6$ kHz. In this case a negative stepped downward leader and negative first return stroke $T_1/T_2 = 1/200$ μ s are reproduced. For this purpose, the parameters are:

- $U_c = 25$ MV – static cloud potential – charging voltage of cloud to ground
- $R_0 = 500 \Omega$ – resistance of overall discharge circuit for negative downward flash $\rightarrow I_{RS,max} \approx U_c/R_0 = 50$ kA
- $C_c = 0.572 \mu$ F – charged cloud capacitance
 $\rightarrow \tau_0 = R_0 \cdot C_c = 286 \mu$ s; $T_2 \approx \ln(2) \cdot \tau_0 \approx 200 \mu$ s
- $k = 10$ – number of steps of downward leader (without final jump)

- $U_1 = U_c/k = 2.5$ MV – charging voltage of one step stage of downward leader
- $R_1 = 50$ k Ω – resistance of one step stage of downward leader
- $C_1 = 2$ nF – capacitance of one step stage of downward leader $\rightarrow \tau_1 = R_1 \cdot C_1 = 100 \mu$ s
- $\Delta t_1 = 250 \mu$ s – time difference between successive steps of downward leader
- $k \cdot \Delta t_1 = 2.5$ ms – downward leader development time

Fig. 15: Equivalent capacitance circuit of the enlarged object simulation, including a stepped downward leader process (stages 4 to 9 - leader and 4 to 19 - creeping discharge, are omitted)

The entire simulated process with stepped downward leader, creeping spark flashover, upward connecting leader with final jump and negative first return stroke is shown in Fig. 16. The process of the upward growing creeping discharge modeled here with steps can be seen in the lower diagram of Fig. 16 as time-shifted voltage breakdowns. The pre-growth of the creeping spark is extremely fast and requires only about 130 ns in the simulation.

Fig. 16: Time development of stepped downward leader to first return stroke (top) and of creeping discharge to flashover in about 2.26103...2.26116 ms = 130 ns (bottom)

V. CONCLUSION

The temporal development of an air discharge in the presence of an insulating material rod in almost homogeneous electric field of a sphere-plate electrode arrangement at an applied pulse voltage was investigated. This arrangement is intended to represent the pre-discharge process in the presence of a lightning strike on a thin protruding object made of insulating material or with low conductivity.

Using network simulations in the time domain, transient FEM simulations, and pulse voltage tests on downscaled arrangements in the laboratory, the evolution of creeping discharges and flashover on the insulator rod could be shown and described. It can be seen that already during the propagation of the creeping spark, some Amps to several 100 A flow into the discharge channel to allow a sufficient amount of charge to move to the tip of the insulator rod and to allow an upward leader to start from the rod tip towards the descending downward leader (tip). The flashover of the insulator rod requires only a few 100 ns, depending on the length and the insulating material of the rod and the applied pulse voltage or the occurring background field strength. This means that there is hardly any time delay for starting an upward (connecting) discharge on a conductor rod.

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